

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 121

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 121

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 121:0 A Song of Ascents.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 121:1</p>
<p>Psa. 121:1 I will ^alift up my eyes to ^bthe mountains;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">From where shall my help come?</p> <p>² My ^ahelp <i>comes</i> from the LORD, Who ^bmade heaven and earth.</p> <p>³ He will not ^aallow your foot to slip; He who ^bkeeps you will not slumber.</p> <p>⁴ Behold, He who keeps Israel Will neither slumber nor sleep.</p>	<p>אֶל-הַהָרִים מֵאֵין יבֹא עֵזְרִי : ² עֵזְרִי מֵעַם יְהוָה עֲשֵׂה שָׁמַיִם וְאָרֶץ : ³ אֶל-יָתֵן לְמוֹט רַגְלֶךָ אֶל- יָנוּם שְׁמֹרֶךָ : ⁴ הִנֵּה לֹא-יָנוּם וְלֹא- יִישָׁן שׁוֹמֵר יִשְׂרָאֵל : ⁵ יְהוָה שְׁמֹרֶךָ יְהוָה צִלְּךָ עַל-יַד יְמִינֶךָ : ⁶ יוֹמָם הַשֶּׁמֶשׁ לֹא-יִכָּכֶה וַיְרִתַּת בַּלַּיְלָה : ⁷ יְהוָה יִשְׁמְרֶךָ מִכָּל-רָע יִשְׁמֹר אֶת- נַפְשֶׁךָ : ⁸ יְהוָה יִשְׁמֹר-צֵאתְךָ וּבֹאֶךָ מִעַתָּה וְעַד-עוֹלָם :</p>
<p>Psa. 121:5 The LORD is your ^akeeper; The LORD is your ^bshade on your right hand.</p> <p>⁶ The ^asun will not smite you by day, Nor the moon by night.</p> <p>⁷ The LORD will ^{1a}protect you from all evil;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">He will keep your soul.</p> <p>⁸ The LORD will ^{1a}guard your going out and your coming in ^bFrom this time forth and forever.</p>	

References

Psalm 121:1

^aPs 123:1; Is 40:26

^bPs 87:1

Psalm 121:2

^aPs 124:8

^bPs 115:15

Psalm 121:3

^a1 Sam 2:9; Ps 66:9

^bPs 41:2; 127:1; Is 27:3

Psalm 121:5

^aPs 91:4

^bPs 16:8; 91:1; Is 25:4

Psalm 121:6

^aPs 91:5; Is 49:10; Jon 4:8; Rev 7:16

Psalm 121:7

¹Or *keep*

^aPs 41:2; 91:10-12

Psalm 121:8

¹Or *keep*

^aDeut 28:6

^bPs 113:2; 115:18

Targum

Psa. 121:1 A song that was uttered on the ascents of the abyss. I will lift up my eyes to the mountains. Whence shall come my help? ² My help is from the presence of the LORD, who made heaven and earth. ³ He will not allow your foot to falter, your guardian does not slumber. ⁴ Behold, he does not slumber and he will not sleep, the guardian of Israel. ⁵ The LORD will guard you, the LORD will overshadow you, on account of the mezuzah affixed on your right side as you enter. ⁶ By day, when the sun rules, the morning-demons will not smite you, nor will the liliths, at night, when the moon rules. ⁷ The word of the LORD will guard you from all harm, he will guard your soul. ⁸ The LORD will guard your going out for business and your coming in to study Torah, from now and forevermore.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm is not called a song of Ascents but is dedicated to the Ascents. Israel finds strength to attain divine heights and will ascend to the LORD's glorious presence. To do this, Israel must abandon its faith in earthly powers and lift its eyes to the LORD. Mortal protectors of the people are failing and unreliable.

Notes of the Psalm

The entire Psalm is a spiritual awareness song that every person who wishes to ascend into Heaven and be in the LORD's presence needs to understand. It is not the powers of the Earth, that are mortal powers, that will bring a person into Heaven. Rather, it will be one's trust and faith in the LORD that will offer salvation. The psalmist says it is up to the individual whether the person will arrive in Heaven when the time is over on Earth.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

